

2RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: TILAHUN****FIRST NAME: GEZAHEGN G.****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Literature contributes to multiple part of a research except:

- Result.**¹
- Introduction and Background.
- Methodology.
- Discussion and conclusion.

2. Which of the following is true about research hypothesis except?

- It is a speculative statement.
- Allows to be focused and guide to collect the required information only.

1. James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 31–32.

- Some prior knowledge is required to formulate hypothesis.
- It is formulated for all type of research.²**
3. Plagiarism can be prevented by:
- Copying the work of others correctly.
- Paraphrasing the author's text in our own words.³**
- Cut and pasting from the internet.
- Quoting directly without acknowledging the source.
4. Which one of the following is false about Research bias?
- Bias distorts research outcome.
- Bias is always unintentional.⁴**
- Bias can be managed to minimize its effect in our research.
- Any interest or predetermined outcome ahead of the study can lead to bias.
5. The purpose of literature review is:
- Provide a current understanding of the subject and its significance.
- Guide the development of research questions.
- Indicates research methodologies used in previous studies.

2. Ibid., 34.

3. Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

4. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 8.

All of the above⁵

6. Which of the following is false about academic essay writing?

- It is always based on evidence to communicate ideas.
- Unpublished material can be used as a source for the arguments.
- It must contain references.

Always Consider evidence that agrees with what we are arguing.⁶

7. Which of the following elements contribute to the successful dissertation?

- Collaboration with other researchers in the field.
- Integration with similar works in the field.
- Effective writing and communication skill.

All⁷

8. Which of the following information is required to cite the sources in our paper properly?

- Who was responsible for creating the source?
- What title or other data identify it?
- Who published it? When? Where can it be found?

5. Ibid., 31.

6. Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 9.

7. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 10–14.

All of the above.⁸

9. The purpose of citing sources in our research paper is:

- To give credit and recognition to the work others have done.
- To get trust in our work by readers on the reliability of facts used in our paper.
- To link our work with others in the field.

All.⁹

10. Which one of the following is true about the quotation?

- It involves extracting exact words or ideas and citing their sources appropriately.**¹⁰
- Quotation mark is always applied even if the length of the sentences is very long.
- There is no room to improve the spelling errors in our paper, even if there are errors in the original sources.
- All of them are true.

8. Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., 9th edition., Chicago guides to writing, editing, and publishing (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 42–43.

9. *Ibid.*, 139–140.

10. *Ibid.*, 371.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.